

Preliminary Study on Biogenic Synthesis and Characterization of Sulfur Nanoparticles from Sulfur-Rich Agricultural Residues

*H. S. Usman¹, F. Audu², M. I. Danja³, I. Y. Sani¹, A. Salihu¹, and A. B. Sallau¹

¹Department of Biochemistry, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

²Department of Biochemistry, University of Abuja, FCT, Nigeria

³Federal University of Education, Zaria, Nigeria

Abstract

Biogenic synthesis is a productive, eco-friendly, one-pot process that produces sulfur nanoparticles (SNPs) without utilizing harmful chemicals. Using a green approach on onion and cabbage peels, SNPs were created in a single step for the current investigation. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) Spectroscopy was utilized to ascertain the nanoparticles' size and intensity, while Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and UV/Visible Spectroscopy were employed to evaluate the biosynthesized SNPs. Results obtained from this study revealed an absorption spectrum at 267nm by onion peels; a characteristic of SNPs formation. However, there was no clear distinct peak indicating formation of SNPs using cabbage peels. FTIR spectra of SNPs and control (onion peel extract) exhibited broad intense peaks at 1028.1 cm^{-1} and 1005.7 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating a marginal shift and presence of flavanones (polyphenols) adsorbed on the surface of the nanoparticles. DLS Spectroscopy results showed dimension of nanoparticles within the range of 40 to 100nm. Synthesis of SNPs using citric acid alone revealed nanoparticles with dimension within the range of 1-3nm, implying the suitability of citric acid alone as a degrading agent in biogenic synthesis of sulphur-nanoparticles using onion peels. With citric acid as the only degrading agent on onion peel, the current study has demonstrated a quick and environmentally friendly method for the biogenic synthesis of sulfur nanoparticles. Further research should be geared towards application of the synthesized SNPs alongside advanced characterization techniques.

Keywords: Biogenic-synthesis, Sulphur-nanoparticles, Agro-residues, Onion-peels, Characterization

Introduction

The production of nanoparticles utilizing biological systems to enhance different biomimetic engineering techniques, has garnered a lot of attention from the scientific community in recent years. If a material's size or one of its dimensions falls between 1 and 100 nm, it is considered a nanomaterial. The use of nanomaterials has a long history, and people have long employed them for a variety of purposes without realizing it. Humans used

asbestos nanofibers to strengthen ceramic mixes approximately 4500 years ago (Heiligtag and Niederberger, 2013). Nanoparticle (NP) research and development has grown rapidly, producing impressive results in a range of synthetic techniques and promising novel applications. The unique quantum-size, high specific surface areas, and better reactivity of NPs over their bulk counterparts are the primary causes of their exceptional features (Vijayan et al., 2016).

Sulfur is one of these reactive nanomaterials that has gained interest lately because of its abundance and range of uses, which include gas sensors, catalysis, antibacterial agents, and anti-cancer agents, among others. In the industrial sector, sulfur has been utilized extensively for the vulcanization of rubber, rechargeable batteries, pulp and paper, fertilizers, sulfuric acid, and antibacterial agents (Boyd, 2016). Additionally, sulfur has been utilized as an antidote for acute exposure to radioactive materials and as an ingredient in formulations for a variety of skin conditions, including dandruff shampoos and acne ointments (Parcell, 2002).

When compared to established physical and chemical methods, the green synthesis approach, which uses biological specimens like plants, yeasts, algae, and fungi, has become a simple, economical, and environmentally friendly method because these organisms are dependable, economical, capable, simple, and easily accessible (Matussin et al., 2020).

Agricultural residues (agroresidues) encompass organic materials obtained as byproducts following harvesting and processing of agricultural crops, such as onion, garlic, orange, and cabbage peels, as well as cane bagasse, pea peels, wheat, and rice straw. Agro-residues are a cheap source of natural cellulosic fibres that are renewed every year. Nigeria is one of the places where these plentiful agro-residues are still a waste. These precious agricultural residues are thrown away or burned because they have no other commercial purpose. Therefore, investigating a viable use of agro-residues will benefit the environment and the economy (Chanana et al., 2016).

According to a previous study by Salem et al., 2016a, *Punica granatum* (pomegranate) peels were utilized to synthesize SNPs using sodium thiosulphate, the resulting nanoparticles had an average particle size of 50nm. Neem leaf SNPs was also synthesized and characterized by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), UV visible spectrophotometer and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) for functional characteristics. Dynamic light scattering measurements for particle size (nm) showed that the particle size was in the range of 35-40 nm (Choudhary et al., 2023).

Sulphur nanoparticles have been successfully prepared from sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) using aqueous garlic extract (*Allium sativum*). The resulting sulphur nanoparticles were examined by Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy, X-ray Diffraction and Scanning Electron Microscopy. The results showed that the size of SNPs synthesized in the presence and absence of aqueous garlic extract were 55.613 and 70.908nm respectively (Khairan et al., 2019).

Sulfur nanoparticles (SNPs) were synthesized by a simple green procedure using *Melia azedarach* leaves aqueous extract and citric acid. The leaves of *Melia azedarach* aqueous extract acts as a capping and stabilizing agent in the formation of sulfur nanoparticles. The average particle size diameter was found to be 16-20 nm (Salem et al., 2016b). A recent study demonstrated UV-VIS Spectroscopy, SEM, TEM, HRTEM, and FTIR investigations, on gSNPs of *Cannabis sativa* leaf extracts, revealing an average size of 20 nm and a spherical morphology (Dasauni et al., 2024)

Presently, there is paucity of data on utilization of agroresidues for SNP formation. Also, there is no report till date on the synthesis of SNPs using the agroresidues (onion and cabbage peels). Hence, this study demonstrates a simple biogenic manufacturing of sulphur nanoparticles, extending the spectrum of beneficial applications of these underutilized biomaterials. In lieu of this, our research focus was a preliminary design based on synthesis and characterization of underutilized sulphur-rich agroresidues like onion and cabbage peels for green synthesis of sulphur nanoparticles (SNPs), adopting 'conversion of waste to wealth' concept.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Conical flask, beaker, glass rod, water bath, weighing balance, measuring cylinder, test tubes, test tube racks, nitric acid (HNO_3), hydrochloric acid (HCl), sodium thiosulphate pentahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$), distilled water, deionized water, Centrifuge, UV-Vis Spectrophotometer, FTIR Spectrometer and DLS Spectrometer.

Preparation of Plant Extract

Brassica oleracea and *Allium cepa* were purchased from Samaru in Kaduna State, Sabon Gari Local Government Area. After that, the fruits were verified at Ahmadu Bello University Zaria's Herbarium Unit, Botany Department, where voucher specimen numbers ABU012068 (*Allium cepa*) and ABU06821 (*Brassica oleracea*) were placed. To get rid of dust and debris, they were first cleaned under running water and then again with deionized water. Peeling was done to obtain agrosidue, which was then shade-dried for three (3) weeks at room temperature before being ground in an electric grinder. In a 200 ml Erlenmeyer flask, 20 g of each plant material was dissolved in 100 ml of deionized water. After two hours of boiling at 100 degrees Celsius, the mixture was filtered through muslin cloth. The filtrate solution was used as the desired plant extract (Tripathi et al., 2018).

Synthesis of Sulphur Nanoparticles (SNPs)

A 3:1 v/v aqua regia solution (nitric acid: hydrochloric acid) was used to cleanse all glasswares before synthesis of sulfur nanoparticles to remove any potential nucleation sites. Sodium thiosulfate pentahydrate (0.078 grams) was fully dissolved in 50 milliliters of deionized water. Each plant extract (20 milliliters) was then added into the aqua regia solution cocktail (3:1 hydrochloric acid and nitric acid). Twenty-five milliliters (25mL) of 20% citric acid were added after the prior reaction mixture had been constantly agitated for five minutes. It took an hour of constant, sporadic stirring of the liquid to see a precipitate. The precipitate was collected by centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 5minutes, followed by washing with distilled water. Synthesized SNP solution was dried at 100 °C in hot air oven until dehydrated, to obtain dried powder (Tripathi et al., 2018).

Characterization of SNPs by UV-Vis, FTIR and DLS spectroscopy

Using UV-Vis spectroscopy (Cary 300 Agilent series), which has a scanning range of 200–700 nm, the as-synthesized SNPs were initially analyzed. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, Cary 630 Agilent series) was used to analyze the SNPs' functional groups. To eliminate impurities, the SNP colloidal suspension was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm. The Onion peels SNP pellet was then washed four times in preparation for FTIR analysis. From 600 to 4000 cm^{-1} , the spectra were recorded. In order to determine the potential size and range of the produced nanomaterial, SNPs were also examined using Dynamic Light Scattering Spectroscopy (DLS-Malvern ZetaSizer, ZEN1600 Instrument, UK).

Results and Discussions

Sulfur nanoparticles (SNPs)

UV-vis spectral investigations were conducted to measure the nanoparticles' absorption peak. Figure 1 shows the UV-Vis spectrum of SNPs. α -sulfur is reported to have an optical absorption maximum (λ_{Max}) between 260 and 280 nm (Heatly and Page, 1952). The peak at 267 nm shows that SNPs were successfully formed (Figure 1). The b2-e3 transition is represented by a secondary peak in Figure 1 at 320 nm, this corroborates previous reported studies (Richardson and Weinberger, 1975, Dasauni et al., 2024). Synthesized SNPs have also been reported to show a peak at about 280 nm (Lesniak et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2022). However, there was no clear distinct peak indicating formation of SNPs for cabbage peels within the range of 260-280nm; as depicted in figure 2; for this reason, only onion peels SNPs were adopted for the rest of the study.

Fig 1 and 2: UV-Vis absorption spectrum of biosynthesized SNPs by onion peels at 267nm (left) and cabbage peels at 228nm (right).

FTIR spectra are used in functional group analysis of synthesized nanoparticles. In the 600–4000 cm^{-1} range, the produced sulfur nanoparticles were scanned using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (Figure 3 and 4). In the FTIR spectra of the SNPs, a significant peak at 2847.7 cm^{-1} indicated –OH stretching, but in the spectrum of the control (onion peel filtrate), this peak migrated to 2851.4 cm^{-1} (Tripathi et al., 2018). In the control spectrum and SNPs, the peak at 2,918.2 cm^{-1} represents the C-H stretching of CH_2 and CH_3 . According to Mehrotra et al. (2017), a peak was seen at 1,796.6 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the aldehyde group's C=O stretching.

The protein's amide link N-H stretching vibration was represented by a peak in the control spectrum at 1524.5 cm^{-1} , which was absent from the original spectrum. S=O stretching of organic sulphate found in sulfones, sulfonyl chloride, and sulfonamide is represented by the band at 1226.3 cm^{-1} for SNPs, which was comparable to the band at 1259.0 cm^{-1} for the control extract (Tripathi et al., 2018). The SNPs and control extract spectra showed a little shift, with broad, strong peaks at 1028.1 and 1005.7 cm^{-1} , respectively. According to Shankar et al. (2004), these peaks resembled the one at 1,074 cm^{-1} and show that flavanones were adsorbed on the nanoparticles' surface.

Fig 3: FTIR spectrum of biosynthesized Sulphur-Nanoparticles using onion peels.

Fig 4: FTIR spectrum of biosynthesized Particles using onion peels filtrate (control)

Figure 5 and 6 shows the DLS (dynamic light scattering) spectra of the as-synthesized SNPs. Results obtained showed that bulk of the synthesized particles were within the range of

40nm- 100nm on the nanoscale (Figure 5); this is in line with the study of Awwad and Abdeen (2015) who characterized SNPs with a size of 60nm using leaves of *Sophora japonica*. Leaves

of *Acanthephylum bracteatum* also revealed SNPs with dimension of 40nm (Javan Kouzegaran and Farhadi, 2017) and 20nm for *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves (Albanna *et al.*, 2016). However, larger sized SNPs were also reported at 89nm for *Azadirachta indica*, 95nm for *Mangifera indica*, 86nm for *Catharanthus roseus* (Paralika and Rai, 2017). Moreover, synthesis of SNPs using citric acid alone revealed nanoparticles with dimension within the range of 1-3nm; this implies the suitability of citric acid alone as a degrading agent in biogenic synthesis of sulphur-nanoparticles. Previous research have also reported SNPs with a

narrow size range of 2-15nm for *Ficus benghalensis* leaves (Tripathi *et al.*, 2019). In the present study, disproportionation reaction was achieved using citric acid alone, without the use of sodium thiosulphide; this is in line with a previous study in which SNPs were synthesized by a simple green procedure using *Melia azedarach* leaves aqueous extract and citric acid (Salem *et al.*, 2016b). Hence, presenting a more cost effective, rapid, and ecofriendly method for the synthesis of sulphur nanoparticles using onion peels.

Fig 5: Dynamic light scattering spectra of SNPs synthesized using onion peels.

Fig 6: Dynamic light scattering spectra of SNPs synthesized from onion peels using citric acid as the degrading agent (Control).

Fig 7: Mechanistic representation of biosynthesis of SNPs from onion peel extract (adopted from Tripathi et al., 2018).

Biosynthesis mechanism

The possible mechanism of SNP biosynthesis is depicted in Figure 7. Polyphenolic compounds, which are abundant in all plant parts such as leaves, fruits, peels, seeds, and flowers, function effectively as reducing agents to reduce reactive oxygen species (Tripathi et al., 2018). Onion peels are rich in polyphenolic compounds. When citric acids and these phytochemicals are mixed, citric acid oxidizes S^{2-} to S^0 and the phytochemicals immediately decrease S^{6+} to S^0 due to the disproportionation process. To reach its optimal size and form, S^0 then undergoes a nucleation process that is influenced by several variables, including temperature, pH, and the kind of reducing and capping agent used (Tripathi et al., 2019; Tripathi and Chung, 2019).

Conclusion

Onion peels were successfully used to synthesize sulfur nanoparticles, followed by characterization. The particles' dimensions fell between 40 and 100 nm. With citric acid as the only degrading agent, the current study has demonstrated a quick and environmentally acceptable method for the biogenic synthesis of sulfur nanoparticles. At the preliminary characterization stage, however, cabbage peels failed to produce a distinct peak indicating successful production of sulfur nanoparticles. Therefore, it can be said that in future research, onion peel nanoparticles may be used to synthesize sulfur nanoparticles. More

imaging techniques should be used in future studies to characterize and optimize reaction conditions, with a greater emphasis on the practical application of SNPs.

Funding Statement

No funding was received for this research work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the assistance of technical staff in multi-user laboratory, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for their support and assistance. We also acknowledge the assistance of Malam Musa in the department of Chemical Engineering, ABU, Zaria.

Authors contribution

Conceptualization: HSU, ABS, AS; Laboratory experiments: IYS, HSU; Data Analysis: HSU, IYS; Writing- original draft preparation: HSU, IYS; Writing-review and editing: HSU, IYS, FA, MID, ABS, AS; Resources: HSU, IYS, FA, MID; Supervision: HSU, ABS, AS. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript

***Correspondence:** H. S. Usman, Department of Biochemistry, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Email: ummisa71@gmail.com or husalisu@abu.edu.ng

References

- Albanna, L. S., Salem, N. M., & Awwad, A. M. (2016). Seed germination and growth of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*): effect of nano-crystalline sulfur. *J. Agric Sci*, 8(10), 219.
- Awwad, A. M., Salem, N. M., & Abdeen, A. O. (2015). Phytochemical and spectral studies of synthesis sulfur nanoparticles using *Sophora japonica* pods extract. *J. Adv. Chem*, 11(3), 3427-3432.
- Boyd, D. A. (2016). Sulfur and its role in modern materials science. *Angewandte Chemie (International ed. in English)*. 55(50): 15486–15502.
- Chanana, B., Parmar, M.S. and Sachdeva, P.K. (2016) Agro-residues: Beyond waste, potential fibres for textile industry. Retrieved from FIBRE2FASHION.COM 17/7/2024
- Choudhary, P., Patel, K. C., Singh, P., Kumawat, S., Raigar, B., & Nath, D. (2023). Green Synthesis of Sulphur Nanoparticles Using *Azadirachta indica* (Neem Leaf) and Its Characterization. *Int. J. Plant. Soil Sci*, 35(23), 441-448.
- Dasauni, K., Nailwal, T.K., & Nenavathu, B.P.N. (2024). Plant extract-mediated biosynthesis of sulphur nanoparticles and their antibacterial and plant growth-promoting activity. *Heliyon*, 10(18), e37797
- Heatley, N. G., & Page, E. J. (1952). Estimation of elemental sulfur by ultraviolet absorption. *Anal. Chem*, 24(11), 1854-1854.
- Heiligtag, F. J., & Niederberger, M. (2013). The fascinating world of nanoparticle research. *Materials today*, 16(7-8), 262-271.
- Javan Kouzegaran, V., & Farhadi, K. (2017). Green synthesis of Sulphur Nanoparticles assisted by a herbal surfactant in aqueous solutions. *Micro and Nano Letters*, 12(5), 329-334.
- Khairan, K., & Jalil, Z. (2019). Green synthesis of sulphur nanoparticles using aqueous garlic extract (*Allium sativum*). *Rasayan J. Chem.*, 12(1), 50-57
- Lesniak, A., Salvati, A., Santos-Martinez, M.J., Radomski, M.W., Dawson, K.A., Åberg, C., (2013) Nanoparticle adhesion to the cell membrane and its effect on nanoparticle uptake efficiency, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 135 (4) 1438–1444
- Matussin, S., Harunsani, M. H., Tan, A. L., & Khan, M. M. (2020). Plant-extract-mediated SnO₂ nanoparticles: synthesis and applications. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng*, 8(8), 3040-3054.
- Mehrotra, N., Tripathi, R. M., Zafar, F., & Singh, M. P. (2017). Catalytic degradation of dichlorvos using biosynthesized zero valent iron nanoparticles. *IEEE Trans. Nanobiosci.*, 16(4), 280-286.
- Paralikar, P., & Rai, M. (2018). Bio-inspired synthesis of sulphur nanoparticles using leaf extract of four medicinal plants with special reference to their antibacterial activity. *Iet Nanobiotech.*, 12(1), 25-31.
- Parcell, S. (2002). Sulfur in human nutrition and applications in medicine. *Alternative Medicine Review: A J. Clin. Ther.* 7(1): 22–44.
- Richardson, N.& Weinberger, P. J. (1975). Electron Spectroscopy and Related Phenomenon. 6: pp109–116.
- Salem, N. M., Albanna, L. S., & Awwad, A. M. (2016a). Green synthesis of sulfur nanoparticles using *Punica granatum* peels and the effects on the growth of tomato by foliar spray applications. *Environ. Nanotechnol. Monit. Manag.*, 6, 83-87.
- Salem, N. M., Albanna, L. S., Awwad, A. M., Ibrahim, Q. M., & Abdeen, A. O. (2016b). Green synthesis of nano-sized sulfur and its effect on plant growth. *J. Agric. Sci.*, 8(1), 188.
- Shankar, S. S., Rai, A., Ahmad, A., & Sastry, M. (2004). Rapid synthesis of Au, Ag, and bimetallic Au core–Ag shell nanoparticles using Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf broth. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 275(2), 496-502.
- Singh, A., Dasauni, K., Nailwal, T., Nenavathu, B.P. (2022) TeO₂ deposited ZnO nanotubes combined with cefotaxime as a nanoantibiotic against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 67, 451–455

Tripathi, R. M., & Chung, S. J. (2019). Biogenic nanomaterials: Synthesis, characterization, growth mechanism, and biomedical applications. *J. Microbiol. Methods*, 157, 65-80.

Tripathi, R. M., Park, S. H., Kim, G., Kim, D. H., Ahn, D., Kim, Y. M., Kwon, S.J., Yoon, S.Y., Kang, H.J. & Chung, S. J. (2019). Metal-induced redshift of optical spectra of gold nanoparticles: An instant, sensitive, and selective visual detection of lead ions. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegrad.*, 144, 104740.

Tripathi, R. M., Rao, R. P., & Tsuzuki, T. (2018). Green synthesis of sulfur nanoparticles and evaluation of their catalytic detoxification of hexavalent chromium in water. *RSC Adv.*, 8(63), 36345-36352.

Vijayan, S. R., Santhiyagu, P., Ramasamy, R., Arivalagan, P., Kumar, G., Ethiraj, K., & Ramaswamy, B. R. (2016). Seaweeds: A resource for marine bio-nanotechnology. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.*, 95, 45-57.